

الدعوة الى الله فى العصر الحاضر مقارنة بين الشرق و الغرب
**DAWAH TO ALLAH IN THE MODERN ERA;
COMPARISON BETWEEN EAST AND WEST**

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ABSTRACT

Dawah, although a single word, can alter severely from one situation to the next. In Islam, the purpose of da'wah is to invite people, Muslims, and non-Muslims and convey the message of tauheed, while leading people to enjoy the good and forbidding the evil. The steps taken to complete a feat as important as dawah must be appropriately chosen along with the inevitable and rapid modernization of today's era. Most scholars opt to give dawah in a one-dimensional and similar way, although not wrong, it may not deliver as planned. This research highlights the fact that no two given dawah are the same and that the methods chosen should be perfectly catered to the receiver of dawah, taking into consideration the atmosphere they were raised in, their audience and their level of thought. In this century the needs of people and their connotation towards religion have changed drastically, this alone is enough to argue that dawah must be given in a proper and solely unique manner as per the situation. This study plans to describe the problem, provide efficient means of solving it, and finally compare how dawah is given in the two main hemispheres, the east, and west. Having experienced the ambience of the west along with the east, along being a daee I have seen and developed updated thoughts towards dawah, and plan to use this knowledge to craft the most optimum way of giving dawah. Finally, all research concludes that the principles of dawah remain the same no matter the time or place only the ways it is presented are adapted to the needs of today's ummah in the East and West.

Keywords: Dawah, Modernization, Connotations, Atmosphere, Dae, Hemispheres, Principles of Dawah, Mukhatab.

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